

HISTORICAL DEVELOPMENT OF THE DUTAR INSTRUMENT IN EASTERN MUSIC CULTURE

Iseeva Ayzada Konisbaevna

Master's student of the Ajiniyaz Nukus State Pedagogical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20378858>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 19th May 2026

Accepted: 21st May 2026

Online: 23rd May 2026

KEYWORDS

dutar, Eastern music, folk instruments, maqom, performance, national heritage, traditional music

ABSTRACT

This scientific thesis examines the emergence, historical formation, and developmental stages of the dutar instrument in the musical culture of Eastern peoples, as well as its role in traditional performance. Additionally, the structure of the dutar, its performance methods, and its significance in regional schools and modern music education are analyzed based on scientific sources.

Introduction: The peoples of the East have had a rich musical culture since ancient times, in which folk musical instruments played a special role. Music, as an integral part of humanity's spiritual life, occupied an important place in rituals, holidays, religious customs, and the life of the people. Among these ancient musical instruments, the dutar stands out for its delicate melody, captivating sounds, and extensive performance capabilities [1. 22].

The dutar is considered the national musical heritage not only of the Uzbek people but also of the Tajik, Turkmen, Karakalpak, Uyghur, and other peoples of the East. For centuries, this instrument has embodied the aesthetic views, spiritual values, and musical thinking of the people [2. 17].

The term "dutor" originates from the Persian-Tajik words "du" — two and "tor" — string, meaning "a two-stringed instrument" [3. 14]. Originally formed as a simple folk instrument, the dutar later became one of the primary instruments of professional musical performance.

According to historical sources, string instruments similar to the dutar appeared in the regions of the ancient East at a very early period. Ceramic statuettes, murals, and miniatures found during archaeological excavations in Central Asia depict musicians playing string instruments [4. 31]. In ancient states such as Bactria, Sogdia, Khwarazm, and Margiana, musical art was developed, and stringed instruments were widely used in ceremonies and celebrations [5. 28]. According to scientists, the first forms of the dutar originated from simple stringed instruments formed in these regions.

The peoples of the Ancient East valued music as an art form that influenced the human psyche. For this reason, string instruments, especially those that produce soft and emotional tones, became popular among the people [6. 19].

Main part: In the 9th–12th centuries, with the beginning of the Eastern Renaissance, the science of music also developed at a high level. The great thinker Abu Nasr al-Farabi, in his work "Kitab al-musiqa al-kabir," provided a scientific analysis of the sound system, modes, and rhythm of musical instruments [7. 63]. Al-Farabi also expressed important thoughts about the influence of string instruments on the human psyche. Abu Ali ibn Sina also emphasized in

his scientific views that music has a positive impact on human health and mental state [8. 22]. This shows that Eastern thinkers viewed music not only as art but also as a science.

The *dutar* is a stringed instrument made of wood. Its main parts are:

bowl; handle; ears; curtains; consisting of strings.

The bowl of the *dutar* is often made of mulberry wood. This is because mulberry wood reflects sound well and enhances resonance [9. 16].

In ancient times, *dutar* strings were made of silk. Silk strings gave the instrument a gentle and soft sound. Currently, synthetic and metal-mixed strings are used [10. 20].

The length and shape of the *dutar* vary depending on the region. For example:

The Khorezm *dutar* has a larger volume and a stronger sound;

The Fergana *dutar* is distinguished by its soft and delicate sound;

The Turkmen *dutar* is famous for having a long handle [11. 44].

The process of making a *dutar* requires great experience and skill. For this reason, the profession of a *dutar* maker is considered one of the important types of folk applied art.

Dutar and *maqom* performance

The *dutar* is considered one of the primary instruments of Eastern *maqom* art. In particular, the *dutar* is widely used in the "Shashmaqom," "Khorezm *Maqoms*" and Fergana-Tashkent *Maqom* paths.

The *dutar* player utilizes various ornaments, intricate finger movements, and rhythmic techniques during the melody's performance. This distinguishes *dutar* performance from other musical instruments.

Several schools of *dutar* performance have been formed in Uzbekistan:

Fergana-Tashkent school;

Bukhara-Samarkand school;

Khorezm school;

Traditions of Karakalpak *dutar* performance.

Today, the *dutar* is considered one of the important directions of national music education. In music and art schools, specialized academic lyceums, and higher educational institutions of the Republic of Uzbekistan, *dutar* performance is taught as a subject.

The *dutar* is of great importance in educating the younger generation in the spirit of national values. Because through national instruments, the history, culture, and traditions of the people are instilled in the minds of young people.

Currently, the *dutar* is widely presented at international festivals and concert programs. This contributes to the global recognition of Uzbek national musical art. The work carried out by UNESCO to preserve intangible cultural heritage has further increased attention to the musical heritage of the peoples of the East, including the art of the *dutar*.

In conclusion, the *dutar* is one of the most ancient and unique musical instruments of the musical culture of the peoples of the East. The history of its formation is closely linked to the civilizations of the ancient East. Over the centuries, the *dutar* has become an integral part of folk music and professional performing arts.

Today, the *dutar* is valued not only as a national instrument but also as a vital art form that embodies the spiritual heritage and aesthetic thinking of the people. Therefore, developing

the art of the dutar, teaching it to the younger generation, and preserving it is one of the urgent tasks.

References:

1. Iseeva, A. "QARAQALPAQ HÁM ÓZBEK DUWTARÍ". Центральноазиатский журнал междисциплинарных исследований и исследований в области управления, 1(5), 35–39. (2024)
2. Karomatov F. O'zbek musiqa tarixi. — Toshkent: Fan, 1978. — B. 17.
3. Vizgo T. O'rta Osiyo xalq cholg'ulari. — Toshkent: Fan, 1980. — B. 14.
4. Akbarov A. Markaziy Osiyo musiqa madaniyati. — Toshkent, 2001. — B. 31.
5. Jabborov A. Sharq musiqa merosi. — Toshkent, 2010. — B. 28.
6. Yunusov R. Milliy musiqa ijrochiligi. — Toshkent, 2007. — B. 19.
7. Abu Nasr Forobiy. Kitob ul-musiqa al-kabir. — Toshkent, 2006. — B. 63.
8. Iseeva, A. "DUWTAR-ÓZBEK MILLIY SAZ ÁSBABÍ" B ACADEMIC RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCE (T. 3, Выпуск 11, сс. 22–27). (2024).
9. Petrosyans D. Cholg'ushunoslik asoslari. — Toshkent, 1991. — B. 16.
10. Odilov A. O'zbek xalq cholg'ularida ijrochilik. — Toshkent, 2005. — B. 20.
11. To'xtasinov S. Dutor ijrochilik maktablari. — Toshkent, 2012. — B. 44.
12. Alimjanovich, Iseev Ruslan. "Fostering the Concerto-Performance Skills of the Pianist." Pioneer: Journal of Advanced Research and Scientific Progress 1, no. 6 (2022): 91-97.
13. Alimjanovich, Iseyev Ruslan. "Peculiarities of Rhodion Schedrin's Piano Cycles." AMERICAN JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND LEARNING FOR DEVELOPMENT 2, no. 3 (2023): 6-15.
14. Alimjanovich, Iseev Ruslan. "FORTEPIANO PANININ JAHAN MUZIKA OQIW PROCESINDEGI AHMIYETI HAM ORNI" MUZIKA HAM KORKEM ONER XABARSHISI (ilimiy-metodikaliq jurnal); 141-145, 2023, ISSN — 2181-4112.